

Cefpodoxime Proxetil associated bloody diarrhoea, itching and red rashes in child: A case report

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Abstract

Date Received: 04/12/2020 Date Revised: 05/01/2021 Date Accepted: 19/02/2021	<p>A case report of a five-year-old paediatric patient was presented here, who received Cefpodoxime proxetil for the treatment of Dengue fever and experienced bloody diarrhoea, itching and red rashes on hands. His laboratory data includes haemoglobin level 10.9 gm % (13-17 gm %), total leucocyte count 4100 /cmm (4000-1000 /cmm), neutrophils 73 % (40-75 %), lymphocytes 20 % (20-45 %), eosinophils 03 % (1-6 %), monocytes 04 % (2-10 %), platelet count 2.42 Lac /cµmm (1.5-4.5 Lac /cµmm), Lymph% 19.9 % (20-45), Gran% 72.5 % (40-75), HGB 10.9/103 /µL (11.0-16.0), HCT 34.9 % (37-54), MCV 68.1 fL (80-100), MCH 21.2 pg, MCHC 31.0 g /dL, RDW-CV 16.2 %, anti-Dengue-IgG and IgM tests are non-reactive and Dengue NS1 antigen test is weakly reactive. The patient recovered from red rashes and bloody diarrhoea after treatment discontinuation. Events bloody diarrhoea and red rashes are probably due to Cefpodoxime Proxetil treatment as per WHO causality assessment.</p>
Keywords Cefpodoxime Proxetil, Dengue Fever, Bloody Diarrhoea, Red Rashes, Discomfort and Malaise	<p>An official publication of Global Pharmacovigilance Society; Published under licence of Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International COPYRIGHT ©2021 Author(s)</p>

Introduction

Dengue is mosquito-borne viral infections caused by RNS virus are one of the most important diseases in the world spread by Aedes mosquitoes. Patients symptoms may be asymptomatic or have acute-onset high fever, dengue fever, dengue haemorrhagic fever (DHF), dengue shock syndrome, muscle and joint pain and myalgia (Hasan *et al.*, 2016). Annually 390 million dengue virus infections (95 % credible interval 284–528 million), of which 96 million (67–136 million) manifest clinically with any severity of disease (Bhatt *et al.*, 2013). The dengue virus belongs genus Flavivirus of the family Flaviviridae, includes four different serotypes (DEN-1, DEN-2, DEN-3, and DEN-4). The dengue cases reported to WHO increased over 8-fold over the last two decades, from 505,430 cases in 2000, to over 2.4 million in 2010, and 4.2 million in 2019. Reported deaths between the year 2000 and 2015 increased from 960 to 4032 (www.who.int). Cefpodoxime Proxetil is third generation cephalosporin with a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity. Cefpodoxime is well tolerated by paediatric patients, with some adverse events related to primarily gastrointestinal tract disturbances and skin rashes like other oral cephalosporins (Fulton *et al.*, 2001). Cephalosporins may cause hypersensitivity reactions, including IgE-mediated, immediate reactions (Kim *et al.*, 2014).

Case description:

A five-year-old male paediatric patient experience high fever and body pain in the early morning on 01 Oct 2020 and visited the hospital on 02 Oct 2020 for general checkup. On 02 Oct 2020, his Dengue NS1 antigen test is weakly reactive, and paediatrician diagnose weakly positive Dengue fever. On same day his laboratory data revealed hemoglobin level is 10.9 gm %, (13-17 gm %), total leucocyte count 4100 /cmm (4000-1000 /cmm), neutrophils 73 % (40-75 %), lymphocytes 20 % (20-45 %), eosinophils 03 % (1-6 %), monocytes 04 % (2-10 %), platelet count 2.42 Lac /cµmm (1.5-4.5 Lac /cµmm), anti-Dengue-IgG and IgM tests are non-reactive. His Widal test of S Typhi 'O' and S Typhi 'H' was negative. His WBC count is 4.1/10⁶/µL (1.0-10.0), Lymph# 0.8/10⁶/µL (0.8-4.0), Gran# 3.0/10⁶/µL (2.0-7.0), Lymph% 19.9 % (20-45), Gran% 72.5 % (40-75), RBC 5.13/10⁶/µL (3.50-5.50), HGB 10.9/10⁶/µL (11.0-16.0), HCT 34.9 % (37-54), MCV 68.1 fL (80-100), MCH 21.2 pg, MCHC 31.0 g/dL, RDW-CV 16.2 %, RDW-SD 41.2 fL, PLT 242/10⁶/µL, MPV 9.6 fL, POW 15.4 %, PCT 0.232 %, P-LCC 63/10⁶/µL and P-LCR 34.2 %. After reviewing his laboratory test reports paediatrician prescribed Cefpodoxime Proxetil 100mg DT tablet, paracetamol suspension and papaya leaf juice twice daily for three days and advise to revisit hospital if fever not disappeared. On 02 Oct 2020 the patient feels discomfort and malaise at the time of taking tablet dissolved in water. On next day patients both hands are red with rashes on it and he is continuously itching for hours. Patient does not experience fever again after starting treatment. On 03 Oct 2020, the patient experience

diarrhoea with blood drops in stool 4 to 6 times a day. On 04 Oct 2020 three tablets of Cefpodoxime proxetil 100 mg DT were discontinued upon appearance of symptoms and only one dose of paracetamol given after symptoms and two doses were discontinued. The diarrhoea frequency decreased on same day and stop on next day and for red rashes form hands completely disappeared after 3 days without antihistaminic drug administered. The patient had a history of fever and paracetamol suspension was tolerated many times without any side effects.

Causality assessment

In pharmacovigilance, causality assessment is a method of finding the relationship between drugs administered and reported adverse drug reactions (Gawai et al., 2020). We assess the causality of events bloody diarrhoea and red rashes by using WHO-UMC causality assessment scale (www.who.int). Causality assessment completed with considering time relationships between the drug administered and the adverse events occurrence, other competing causes (like co-medications and current disease, patient medical history), dechallenge and rechallenge (Rehan et al., 2009). The different causality types are given in Table 1. After assessing above points, we can say bloody diarrhoea and red rashes is probably due to Cefpodoxime Proxetil treatment.

Table 1: The WHO–UMC causality assessment method bases on the following criteria

Causality type	Time relations hip	Other drugs/dis ease ruled out	De-challenge	Re-challenge
Certain	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Probable	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Possible	Yes	No	No	No
Unlikely	No	No	No	No

Discussion

Dengue is mosquito-borne viral infections caused by RNS virus spread by Aedes mosquitoes. Cefpodoxime is cephalosporin with a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity and well tolerated by paediatric patients. Though the Dengue is viral disease the paediatrician prescribed antibacterial treatment which may be off label use of Cefpodoxime Proxetil. Marketing authoritarianism holder of such antibiotic drugs should actively create awareness in health care professional to stop off label use of drugs in paediatric patients as it may leads to dire consequences.

Conclusions

In many published study mention Cefpodoxime is well tolerated in child patients, with some adverse events

related to gastrointestinal tract disturbances and skin rashes like other oral cephalosporins and may cause hypersensitivity reactions. We conclude that bloody diarrhoea and red rashes is probably due to Cefpodoxime Proxetil as it disappeared after treatment discontinued as per WHO causality assessment method.

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None

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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